

al-Jami' al-A'dham Jami' az-Zaytouna al-Ma'mour الجامع الأعظم الزيتونة المعمور

By Bou Ali Malika, Zaytouna

Entry tags: Tunisia, Religious Group, Mosque, Religious Place, Islamic Traditions

Al-Zaytouna Mosque is the first Islamic university, and the first university to teach sciences of all kinds.

Date Range: 698 CE - 2022 CE

Region: ancient medina of Tunis

Region tags: North Africa, Tunisia

In the middle of the ancient medina of Tunis

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: كتاب جامع الزيتونة المعلم ورجاله محمد عزيز بن عاشور . دار سيراس للنشر 1991. تونس
- Source 2: ذكرى مرور ثلاثة عشر قرنا على تأسيس الزيتونة عن الكلية الزيتونية للشريعة وأصول الدين . الدار التونسية للنشر . 1979. تونس

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/229/13/1/43019>
- Source 1 Description: Un article d'une revue académique algérienne concernant l'éducation et l'enseignement dans la grande mosquée au début du XX siècle
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/49/8/2/70796>
- Source 2 Description: Un article d'une revue académique algérienne sur l'influence civilisationnel de la grande mosquée sur l'élite algérienne
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/92/20/4/135584>
- Source 3 Description: Un autre article d'une revue universitaire algérienne à propos de l'activité des étudiants algériens

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Ce n'est pas vraiment une fouille, c'est plutôt un dépouillement de la grande mosquée de son héritage scientifique (livres et revue et surtout les manuscrits...) beaucoup (peut être même des milliers de manuscrits ont été volés lors de leur déplacement vers la bibliothèque nationale

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1956-1958

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Elle n'avait pas de nom officiel

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Mound

– Terracing

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure
– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

↳ One single feature
– Mound

Notes: On a également dit qu'il a été construit sur les ruines d'une cathédrale chrétienne dans laquelle le tombeau de Sainte "Olivia Palerme" ou "Sainte Olive" a été construit par l'empereur Hadrien en 138

Reference: بحث أثري , n.d., فكري , أحمد . "مسجد الزيتونة الجامع في تونس". جامعة الإسكندرية مصر.

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

Notes: Elle a été l'objet de beaucoup de réparation mais sans changer la structure de la grande Mosquée

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: "janaiz" وضحن والسقاية والداموس والعبدية و"الحمودية" مكتبة للمسجد مباني مضافت

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Autour de la grande Mosquée on trouve toute la vie quotidienne des tunisiens mais on trouve aussi beaucoup de mosquée comme celle de la Kasba, de Hammouda Pacha...

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Elle a été l'objet de beaucoup de réparation mais sans changer la structure de la grande Mosquée

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

↳ In modernity
– Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: تتحدّث عن عبادة الإله الواحد عند المسلمين لأنها ديانة توحيدية

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify
– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: يمكن الإشارة إلى أنّ كثيرا من الولاة والأمراء قديما أمروا ببناء الجلمع او تجديده مثل الأمير الوالى "عيد الله بن الحجاب " والأمير "ابراهيم " و أخوه "زبادالله الأعلي" والمستعين بالله

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Tout genre de livre des sciences religieuses, linguistiques logiques et philosophiques

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Yes

Notes: Tout autour des murs de la grande salle de la prière il y avait des bibliothèques pleines de livres

↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

– No

↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:
This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

– Yes

↳ Space underneath the structure

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: هذه الكتب والمخطوطات محفوظة في غرفة

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– Yes

↳ Are they read aloud:

– Yes

↳ To a human audience

– Yes

↳ Are they studied:

– Yes

↳ Are they recopied:

– Yes

↳ Used for divination:

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: La grande Mosquée était la première université dans l'histoire humaine c'est pourquoi on trouve ces livres et ces multiples fonctions

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: هناك بيت الصلاة فيها أعمدة وهو المسجد المستطيل الشكل وأربعة مآذن هرمية اثنان منها ظاهرة؛

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: كل الهياكل البنائية تعتمد في أداء الصلاة

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: La mosquée représente une seul structure de bâtiment

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 90

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 5000

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 43

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1344

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

|

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: بعض الوُورّخين قالوا أنّه استعمل في البداية بقايا حجارة كاثدرائية مسيحية

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: بني الجامع على أنقاض كاثدرائية مسيحية موجود فيها قبر القديسة أوليفيا بالبرموا وقيل أنّه سمي باسم قديسة الزيتون

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: هناك كثير من النقوش على الجصّ في قبة الجامع وقواعده وزخارف على ابواب الجامع والسقوف الخشبية إضافة إلى الأعمدة المحيطة بالبهو الداخلي

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

Notes: هي أشكال هندسيّة ونقوش تتخلّلها نصوص قرآنيّة فيها تعظيم لله تعالى بالخط الكوفي

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: زخارف كثيرة من الفن الإسلامي المغربي والأندلسي و التركي موجودة في اقسام كثيرة من الجامع في القبة ووالمحراب واقواس صحن الجامع وتيجانه جعلته من أهم المعالم المعماريّة الإسلاميّة الأربعة في افريقيا بعد جامع "الفسطاط " وجامع:الناقة " بطرابلس وجامع "عنية " بالقبروان

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– No

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: قد يذكر على بعض النقوش الموجودة في المحراب أو الأعمدة أو القبة أو مدخل الأبواب نصوص تاريخية تتحدث عن سنة الأنشاء ومن قام ببناءه أو تجديده

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: نجد مثلا نسا حول قاعدة القبة المربعة أنها ممّا أمر بعمله الإمام "المستعين بالله " على يد "نصير مةلاه " سنة 150 وانّ الذي صنعها فتح الله

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: I y a une chaire en bois faite en l'an 249 AH de bois, semblable à la mosquée de Kairouan, se déplaçant sur un rail qui entre dans la maqsura après la fin de la prière En plus des lustres en cuivre

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: La Mosquée en générale représente symboliquement l'au-dela par la minaret et le dôme

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: هناك آيات قرآنيّة وأشكال هندسيّة منقوشة مثلا في داخل القباب وحولها

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Nous parlons d'une religion monothéiste dans laquelle l'adorateur communique avec un seul Dieu par la supplication et la louange dans la prière sans l'aide des êtres surnaturels.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: La communication est certainement indirecte et a besoin d'interprétation

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Ce n'est la connaissance religieuse qui est à la base de la communication mais plutôt la piété du croyant

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: Une histoire racontée dit que beaucoup de marabouts assistent aux cercles du dhikr ذکر lors des grandes occasions dangereuses pour la cité de Tunis en particulier et pour les tunisiens en général

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: Vus non entendus oui

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: non

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Des récits racontés par des tunisiens disent que des jinns assistaient à des cours de quelques imminents savants de la grande Mosquée.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: La communication est basée non pas sur le savoir exotérique mais sur la piété du croyant

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: الجامع هو بيت صلاة وعبادة لله الواحد ولذلك يحافظ المصلّون على نظافته ونظافة سجاداته وكما يلتزمون بالعهود التي أقسموا عليها مع الله وفيما بينهم في معاملاتهم اليوميّة

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: La mosquée est un lieu de culte pour les adorateurs du Dieu Unique, et la prière et la supplication sont un moyen de s'adresser à Dieu Tout-Puissant

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Reference: 2021, الحشايشي, محمد بن عثمان . تاريخ جامع الزيتونة. تونس: دار الإمام المازري للنشر والتوزيع.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: A partir de 2 500 participants

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: بحسب المناسبات الدنيّة أو تخرج طلبة التعليم الزيتوني أو دورات حفظ القرآن الكريم

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: بعض الهدايا تقدّم للجامع كصدقات مثل الزرابي و الثريات وسجّادات

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Certains bonbons ou aliments peuvent être offerts lors d'occasions religieuses telles que l'Aïd al-Adha, l'Aïd al-Fitr ou l'anniversaire du Prophète à l'intérieur de la mosquée.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: pour les musulmans

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Des élèves d'âges différents suivent des cours religieux privés à l'intérieur de la mosquée

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: La rénovation de ce monument historique s'est déroulée en plusieurs étapes depuis l'an 114 AH, et de nombreuses pièces y ont été ajoutées, telles que des portes en bois, des dômes, des décorations et la chaire. Aux XIVe et XVIIe siècles, les bâtiments de deux bibliothèques "Al-Hamudiyah" et "Abdalia", le Damous, le Shaqaya et le tribunal "janaiz" ont été ajoutés.

Reference: 1991, ابن عاشور, محمد العزیز . جامع الزيتونة المعلم ورجاله. تونس: دار سراس للنشر .

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: إضافة للقائمين في أماننا الآن على تنظيف المكان فإنّ بلدية مدينة تونس والمعهد الوطني لحماية التراث يقوم بصلنة هذا المعلم التاريخي

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: قد يقوم بعض المتطوعين من التلاميذ والمصلين بأعمال التنظيف خاصة في المناسبات الدينية

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: تقام الإحتفالات و الدروس الدينية و الصلاة داخل قاعة الصلاة وفي بهو المسجد

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Des célébrations ont lieu à l'occasion de fêtes religieuses telles que l'anniversaire du Prophète, le nouvel an Hijri, la bataille de Badr, l'Aïd al-Adha et l'Aïd al-Fitr.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

– Elites

– Non-elites

Notes: يحضر هذه الإحتفالات كلُّ النَّاس من المسلمين كبارا وصغارا وذكورا وإناثا

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Notes: في هذه الأحتفالات هناك طلاء الجدران وتزيين بالإنارة وفوانيس الملونة

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 2500

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Notes: قد يحتفل مثلا بالتلاميذ الحافظين للقرآن الكريم في مناسبة دينية كإحتفال بالمولد النبوي أو رأس السنة "الهجرية"

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: يعتني بجامع الزيتونة وزارة الشؤون الدينية و المعهد الوطني للتراث و بلدية تونس المدينة

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, 2021 الحشايشي, محمد بن عثمان . تاريخ جامع الزيتونة. تونس: دار الإمام المازري للنشر والتوزيع, 2021

Reference: Other [specify]: La rénovation de ce monument historique s'est déroulée en plusieurs étapes depuis l'an 114 AH, et de nombreuses pièces y ont été ajoutées, telles que des portes en bois, des dômes, des décorations et la chaire. Aux XIVe et XVIIe siècles, les bâtiments de deux bibliothèques Al-Hamudiyyah" et "Abdalia", le Damous, le Shaqaya et le tribunal "janaiz" ont été ajoutés., ابن عاشور, محمد, 1991, دار سراس للنشر, تونس: جامع الزيتونة المعلم ورجاله. العزيز.

Reference: Mound, مصر, جامعة الإسكندرية "مسجد الزيتونة الجامع في تونس". فكري, أحمد. n.d.. بحث أثري.